

DEVELOPMENT OF A COMPOSITE FIREWALL FOR MASS TRANSIT APPLICATIONS

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1 Introduction

There is a push within the mass transit industry to reduce weight in order to improve fuel consumption. Many components are now being built using composite materials due to their high stiffness to weight ratio. During this research project the feasibility of building a firewall from composite materials for mass transit vehicles was investigated. The purpose was to reduce the weight of current metallic firewall systems while reducing part counts and remaining cost competitive.

In order to gain approval from transit authorities the composite firewall panel was required to pass the specifications laid out in Federal Transit Administration Docket 90-A – Recommended Fire Safety Practices for Transit Bus and Van Materials Selection [1]. Docket 90-A specifies that the panels must achieve a 15 minute rating according to ASTM E119 – Standard Test Methods for Fire Tests of Building Construction [2]. A panel is considered to have passed when no flame or gases breach the panel and the temperature rise on the unexposed surface does not exceed 139°C.

2 Materials

The test panels were laid up by hand using glass fabrics that included 1.5 oz chopped strand mat (CSM), 10 oz cloth, and 18 oz woven roving (WR). Details of the laminate schedules for each test are provided in the following sections. All of the panels were constructed using Norsodyne H 81269 TF flame retardant polyester resin. When exposed to high temperatures the resin expands and forms a char by-product on the surface of the part. The char layer, and the air pocket it creates, then acts as an insulating layer between the flame and the glass fibres.

Three additional materials were tested to determine their fire protection ability in this application. The first material was Technofire, an intumescent fabric mat that was incorporated into two of the test lay-

ups. Similar to the Norsodyne resin, the Technofire forms a char insulating layer when exposed to heat. The second material was BGF insulation mat with a thickness of 6.35 mm that was applied on the outside surface of the laminates after the panel was cured. The final product was PyroTarp, an intumescent coating that was applied like paint to the fire exposed surface of the laminates after the parts had cured. PyroTarp also formed a char insulating layer when exposed to high temperatures.

3 Test Methods

Three different tests were performed in order to screen potential fire protection methods before performing the ASTM E119 test. In the first test four panel configurations that incorporated the Technofire and BGF insulation mats were tested using ASTM E162 – Standard Test Method for Surface Flammability of Materials Using a Radiant Heat Energy Source [3] in order to calculate the flame spread index (I_s).

During the second test the rise in the backside temperature was measured for panels with and without the PyroTarp coating that were exposed to a blowtorch flame.

In the third test a single propane burner was used in a semi-enclosed chamber to test larger scale panels that were protected using the PyroTarp coating. The temperature ramp rate closely followed the ASTM E119 specification, although the maximum temperature was approximately 100°C below the specified maximum temperature of ASTM E119.

Finally, after the preliminary tests were completed one panel was tested using the ASTM E119 methodology.

4 Results

4.1 ASTM E162

Four different panel configurations were tested using ASTM E162 as shown in Figure 1. The laminate schedules are provided in Table 1.

Fig.1. ASTM E162 test setup

	Laminate Schedule
A	Gelcoat/CSM/WR/CSM/CSM
B	Gelcoat/CSM/WR/CSM/CSM/BGF
C	Gelcoat/CSM/cloth/CSM/WR/CSM/Tech
D	Gelcoat/CSM/cloth/CSM/WR/CSM/Tech/BGF

Table 1. ASTM E162 laminate schedules

	F_s	Q	I_s
A	1.23	7.02	10
B	1.00	5.95	5
C	1.05	6.36	5
D	1.00	4.94	5

Table 2. ASTM E162 results

The flame spread factor (F_s), heat evolution factor (Q), and flame spread index (I_s) were measured for each of the panels. Flame spread factor is a measurement of the rate at which the flame front travels across the panel. Heat evolution factor represents the amount of heat generated during the burn process. The flame spread index is the product of the flame spread factor and the heat evolution factor.

The results are summarized in Table 2. The flame spread factor was similar for the four panels, although the panels that used either Tecmat or Technofire had the best performance. The heat evolution factor was reduced by using either the Tecmat or the Technofire. However, the lowest value was obtained by using both of them in combination. The flame spread index was reduced from 10 to 5 by using any of the additional fire protection materials. This is well below the allowable value of 35 specified by FTA Docket 90 for most bus components.

4.2 PyroTarp Blowtorch Test

One of the big concerns for the firewall design was the rise in the backside temperature. A blowtorch test was performed to make a preliminary determination of the effectiveness of PyroTarp in preventing a rise in temperature on the unexposed surface. Two panels were tested, one with PyroTarp applied to the non-gelcoat surface and one without any additional protection. Both panels had a layout of [Gelcoat/CSM/cloth/CSM/WR/CSM].

A blowtorch was then used to apply an open flame to both panels for 15 minutes while the backside temperature was measured. The flame temperature was approximately 980°C.

During the blowtorch test of the PyroTarp samples the rise in the unexposed surface temperature was 258°C for the uncoated specimen after 15 minutes, but was only 167°C for the panel coated using PyroTarp.

After the testing was complete the panels were cut and the internal damage was examined. Delamination had occurred in the panel with PyroTarp, but the back ply appeared to be undamaged as shown in Figure 2. Delamination was also observed in the panel without PyroTarp, but the back ply was clearly damaged as shown in Figure 3.

Fig.2. Undamaged back ply for panel with PyroTarp

Fig.3. Damaged back ply for panel without PyroTarp

4.3 Single Propane Burner Test

A small scale single propane burner test was performed to replicate the ASTM E119 test. The major differences include a smaller test panel (609.6 mm x 609.6 mm instead of 1219.2 mm x 1219.2 mm), one burner instead of a series of burners, and a test enclosure that is only semi-enclosed. The temperature/time curve used during the testing is compared to the specified ASTM E119 curve in Figure 4. The rate of increase is similar at the start of the test, but by the 30 minute time interval the single propane burner test is approximately 100°C colder (730°C compared to 843°C).

Two panels were tested during the single propane burner open flame test. Both panels had a layout of [Gelcoat/CSM/cloth/CSM/WR/CSM] and both panels were coated with PyroTarp on the fire exposed (non-gelcoat) surface. The PyroTarp was chosen over the Technofire and BGF mat for two major reasons. The first reason is that the BGF mat is only rated to 650°C while temperatures reach 845°C during the ASTM E119 test. The second reason was the cheaper cost of the PyroTarp compared to the Technofire. This application was very cost sensitive so the cheapest alternatives that could accomplish the task had to be chosen.

One of the panels had a 6.8 kg weight attached to the unexposed surface to represent systems attached to the firewall panel. The weight was used to help determine if the firewall panel could continue to carry a load if the structural integrity of the panel was reduced during the test. Each panel was tested for 30 minutes with 10 thermocouples attached to the backside of the panel to measure the rise in temperature. The positions of the thermocouples are shown in Figure 5.

Fig.4. Single propane burner temperature/time curve compared to specified ASTM E119 curve

Fig.5. Thermocouple positions

The charring due to the intumescent coating and resin was clearly visible on both panels as shown in Figure 6. The temperature changes over time for the panels with and without the weight are shown in Figures 7 and 8.

After 30 minutes the flame had not penetrated either of the test panels. When the test was stopped at 30 minutes the average temperature rise for the panel without the weight was 86.3°C and the highest individual temperature rise was 148.2°C. The average temperature rise for the panel with the weight was 86.2°C, but the maximum individual temperature rise was only 108.3°C. It appears that the weight acted as a heat sink and redistributed the heat across the face of the panel resulting in a more even temperature distribution. Both tests were well below the allowable 139°C rise of the average temperature. As well, despite the damage caused by the fire, the panel with the weight attached to the back did not show any obvious signs of being unable to support the load.

After the testing was complete the panels were cut into quarter sections in order to examine the internal damage. Figure 9 shows that delamination occurred in the panel without the weight between the back 1.5 oz CSM ply and the rest of the laminate. The 1.5 oz CSM ply appears relatively undamaged whereas significant damage can be observed in the remaining plies. It is thought that the air gap created when the delamination occurred acted as an insulating layer and helped to protect the back 1.5 oz CSM ply. Figure 10 shows that there was only minimal damage in the panel with the weight. This may be due to the redistribution of heat by the weight from hot spots to cooler areas.

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Fig.6. Panel charring due to intumescent coating and resin during single propane burner testing

Fig.7. Backside temperatures for panel without weight

Fig.8. Backside temperatures for panel with weight

Fig.9. Delamination of panel without the weight

Fig.10. Delamination of panel with the weight

4.4 ASTM E119 Test

A 1219.2 mm x 1219.2 mm panel using the same layout as the single propane burner test, and with a coating of PyroTarp on the non-gelcoat side, was then tested using the ASTM E119 method. Five thermocouples were positioned at the centre and quarter points of the panel on the unexposed surface. A temperature/time curve showing the measured furnace temperature compared to the standard ASTM E119 curve is shown in Figure 11.

During this test the maximum allowable average temperature rise is stated as 139°C and the maximum individual temperature rise is 181°C. The average temperature rise of 139°C was exceeded after 4.3 minutes and the maximum individual temperature rise was exceeded after 10.3 minutes as shown in Figure 12.

It was noted that the surface of the panel ignited at 1.5 minutes and subsequently self-extinguished at 2.5 minutes. Re-ignition was noted at 5 minutes with heavy flaming on the exposed surface that continued until the test was ended after 11 minutes. It should be noted that no flame penetration had occurred at this time.

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Fig.11. Furnace temperature/time curve compared to specified ASTM E119 curve. Blue is the average furnace temperature. Pink is the standard curve.

Fig.12. Backside temperatures for ASTM E119 test. Red is the average temperature. Blue is the maximum temperature

5 Conclusions

The results from initial surface flammability (ASTM E162) and single propane burner tests of a composite firewall were encouraging. However, the test panel failed to meet the 15 minute pass rating as specified in ASTM E119. It is believed that the difference in the test results between the single propane burner test and the actual ASTM E119 test were due to the use of more than one heat source in the ASTM E119 test and the fact that the furnace was fully enclosed. This meant that the entire furnace was at the maximum temperature, while in the single propane burner test only a small area at the tip of the flame was exposed to the maximum temperature.

Due to the cost sensitivity of this particular application the Technofire mat was not included in the ASTM E119 test panel laminate schedule. This material showed promise in the initial tests and should be included in future tests as it may improve performance.

Future testing should also determine the effect of using an infusion manufacturing method instead of hand layup. Changing to infusion processing should increase the glass content of the panel. It is thought that an increase in glass content will improve the fire retardancy of the panel, but this possible improvement has not been quantified yet.

During the single propane burner test it appeared that the air gap created in the laminate after delamination helped to insulate the back plies and helped to protect them from damage. This indicates that a dual wall system that consists of a laminate, air gap, and then a second laminate may slow the temperature rise on the unexposed surface as well as protect the back plies from damage. Another related possibility may be to create a composite sandwich panel. The low thermal conductivity value of the core material would potentially slow the increase in temperature on the unexposed surface. However, testing would have to be performed to determine a suitable core material that would not immediately ignite under high temperatures.

References

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